

STEPUPIORS

Twinning for a European Consortium of Rectal Cancer Research Institutions through Stepping up Scientific, Technological and Innovation Excellence of IORS

Funded by
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INSTITUT ZA ONKOLOGIJU
I RADIOLOGIJU SRBIJE

**M5.1 Established Research Management office at IORS
within WP5 of the STEPUPIORS project**

The objectives of WP5 - Research and project management, within M5.1 were set out to establish a Research Management Office (RMO) at the Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia (IORS) by training IORS staff on pre- and post-grant project management activities with expert advice from partner institutions' project management office members and external trainings.

Milestone No: M5

Deliverable Name: Established Research Management office at IORS

Type: DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

Dissemination Level: PU – Public

Due Date: March 31, 2023

Delivery Date: March 29, 2023

Status: Achieved

The IORS Director issued a Decision to form a Pilot Research Management Team at IORS on March 08, 2023, that would serve as a prototype for the RMO. The Team consists of WP5 staff, the Head of IORS Scientific Department, the Head of IORS Procurement Department, the Head of IORS Legal Department, the Head of IORS Financial Department and representatives of laboratory technical staff. The document was published on the IORS website (<https://www.ncrc.ac.rs/uncategorized-sr/vesti/stepupiors-horizont-evropa-projekat-101079217/>) and the project website Important Documents section (<https://www.stepupiors.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/D5.2-STEPUPIORS.pdf>; <https://www.stepupiors.eu/2023/03/newsevents/establishment-of-a-research-management-team-at-iors-d5-2/>).

The Team will liaise project activities between the IORS research team and the local legal, administrative, procurement and human resources IORS staff to enable a more effective project flow. The team will perform risk mitigation continuously during the project. The Team will also strive to coordinate other pre-award and post-award processes at IORS and future intellectual property applications at the national and international level in the next 3 years and report to the Director on the outcomes.